

Redox Reactions in Non-aqueous Media. Determination of Xanthates and Organotrithiocarbonates (Thioxanthates) with Iron(III) in Acetonitrile

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The use of iron(III) perchlorate (in acetonitrile) for the visual, potentiometric and spectrophotometric determination of xanthates and organotrithiocarbonates (thioxanthates) in acetonitrile medium is described. The proposed methods are simple, accurate and reliable and show the promise of wide applicability.

IRON(III) is a powerful oxidant in acetonitrile. This has been attributed to the stabilisation of iron(II) relative to iron(III) by solvation. Consequently, the potential of $Fe^{III}-Fe^{II}$ couple is increased markedly. The value of formal reduction potential is 1.57 V vs silver, 0.01 M silver nitrate reference electrode¹. Coetzee and Campion² found the potential of $Fe^{III}-Fe^{II}$ couple to be 1.3 V greater in acetonitrile than in water. The present paper describes the application of iron(III) perchlorate for the determination of xanthates $RO.CS.S^-$ and organotrithiocarbonates (thioxanthates) $RS.CS.S^-$ in acetonitrile medium.

Experimental

Acetonitrile was distilled twice over phosphorus pentoxide (5 g dm^{-3}). Xanthates and organotrithiocarbonates were prepared and purified by the reported methods³⁻⁵. Iron(III) perchlorate (Fluka) standard solution was prepared by dissolving a little more than the calculated amount of the compound in acetonitrile. The solution was standardised¹ by potentiometric titration with potassium iodide in acetonitrile. Diphenylamine in acetonitrile was used as 0.1% solution.

Potentiometric titrations were performed with a Toshniwal CLO6A potentiometer using platinum wire as indicator electrode and modified-calomel electrode (saturated methanolic KCl used instead of aqueous solution) as the reference. Spectrophotometric titrations were performed with a Bausch and Lomb spectrophotometer.

Procedure :

Visual and potentiometric procedures : Aliquots of the solutions in acetonitrile of each xanthate and trithiocarbonate were taken in dry titration vessels and the volume made to 30-40 ml with acetonitrile. Each solution was titrated at room temperature ($\sim 25^\circ$) with the standard 0.02 M iron(III) perchlorate solution. The end-point could be detected

potentiometrically or visually (with or without indicator). On adding the reagent, xanthate and trithiocarbonate solutions became reddish brown and wine red, respectively. The intensity of each colour increased to its maximum. Thereafter, each colour started decreasing and finally the solution turned colourless at end-point, which was extremely sharp. The visual titrations could also be performed by using diphenylamine indicator (1-2 drops) to a blue end-point. The colour-changes during the titration were almost the same as in the titration without indicator. Potentiometric titrations gave plots with two well defined breaks at Fe^{III} to xanthates or trithiocarbonate ratio of 0.33 and 1.0. The results as calculated on the basis of second break are given in Table 1.

Spectrophotometric titration procedure : Aliquots of solutions in acetonitrile of each xanthate and trithiocarbonate were taken in colorimetric tubes and the volume made to 6 ml with acetonitrile. The titration was commenced by adding standard iron(III) perchlorate solution in small instalments, stirring the solution with a specially designed magnetic stirring disc each time and measuring the absorbance at 550 and 530 nm, respectively (wavelengths corresponding to the maximum absorbance of Fe^{II} salts of these compounds) against a reagent blank. The results are presented in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The results of determination indicate that the oxidation of xanthates and trithiocarbonates with iron(III) perchlorate in acetonitrile proceeds in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The appearance of reddish brown and wine red colours in the titrations respectively of xanthates and trithiocarbonates indicate the formation of iron(II) salts of these compounds, which are oxidised to the dixanthogens and bis(alkyl/aryl-mercaptopthiocarbonyl)disulphides in the later part

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF XANTHATES RO-C(=S)SK AND TRITHIOCARBONATES RS-C(=S)SK WITH IRON(III) PERCHLORATE IN ACETONITRILE

R	Amount taken = 4 mg Amount found (± 0.03 - 0.04 mg)			Amount taken = 8 mg Amount found (± 0.05 - 0.07 mg)		
	Visual method		Potentiometric method	Visual method		Potentiometric method
	Without indicator	With indicator (diphenylamine)		Without indicator	With indicator (diphenylamine)	
<i>Xanthates</i>						
Ethyl	4.02	4.03	3.99	8.06	8.08	8.04
n-Propyl	3.97	3.98	4.01	7.94	7.96	8.03
Isopropyl	3.97	4.02	4.01	7.95	7.94	7.97
Isobutyl	4.02	3.97	3.99	8.06	8.08	8.03
n-Amyl	4.03	4.02	3.98	7.96	8.05	7.98
Isoamyl	3.98	3.99	3.98	8.06	8.07	8.04
<i>Trithiocarbonates</i>						
Ethyl	4.03	3.98	4.00	7.93	7.95	8.02
Isobutyl	4.00	4.02	4.00	8.04	7.96	7.98
n-Butyl	3.98	3.97	3.99	8.06	7.96	8.02
n-Hexyl	3.99	4.02	4.01	7.95	8.04	7.98
Benzyl	4.02	3.98	4.02	7.94	8.05	8.05
Dodecyl	3.97	4.02	3.98	8.07	7.94	8.05

TABLE 2—SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC TITRATIONS OF XANTHATES RO-C(=S)SK AND TRITHIOCARBONATES RS-C(=S)SK WITH IRON(III) PERCHLORATE IN ACETONITRILE

R	Xanthates		R	Trithiocarbonates	
	taken = 0.6 mg Amount found ± 0.004 - 0.006 mg	taken = 0.9 mg Amount found ± 0.006 - 0.009 mg		taken = 0.35 mg Amount found ± 0.002 - 0.004 mg	taken = 0.70 mg Amount found ± 0.004 - 0.006 mg
	Ethyl	0.605		0.893	Ethyl
n-Propyl	0.596	0.895	n-Butyl	0.352	0.695
Isopropyl	0.597	0.907	Isobutyl	0.347	0.695
Isobutyl	0.595	0.906	n-Hexyl	0.349	0.698
n-Amyl	0.604	0.893	Benzyl	0.353	0.703
Isoamyl	0.596	0.897			

of the titration. These observations clearly indicate that the oxidation of these compounds proceed in two stages. From the titre value (particularly with the potentiometric method), it can be inferred that the first stage corresponds to their oxidation to disulphides with the simultaneous formation of their iron(II) salts. The second stage corresponds to the oxidation of these salts. The following two stages of oxidation are represented for xanthates,

Similar reactions can be written for trithiocarbonates. This is further supported by spectrophotometric titration. The increase of absorbance arises due to the production of coloured iron(II) salts. In the second step, the iron(II) salts are oxidised, thereby causing a decrease in absorbance to virtually zero. No more coloured species are formed with

further addition of the titrant beyond the end-point which may be calculated on the basis of either of the intersections.

These observations reveal that in the acetonitrile medium, iron(III) salts could serve as useful reagents for the routine determination of xanthates and organotrithiocarbonates.

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